

CHEMISTRY

NEW RECYCLING AND UTILIZATION ROUTE FOR NYLON 6,6 WASTE PLASTIC THROUGH THERMOCHEMICAL CdS NANOPARTICLE DEPOSITION

Malikov E.

*Baku State University, Chemistry department, Azerbaijan
Ph.D. in Chemistry, ORCID: 0000-0002-7424-6228*

Abstract

Nylon 6,6 is a thermoplastic material that is used in the production of a wide variety of useful things from synthetic fibers and packaging substances to cable ties and films, etc. Due to the high amount of production and application it causes danger to the environment with accumulation in nature. The solution to the problem is the utilization of its wastes. Nylon 6,6 based plastic waste materials were used in this work as the matrix for the synthesis of the CdS nanoparticles in order to get a new advanced polymer nanocomposite with unique properties and to find novel utilization for the waste plastics. Cadmium chloride and sodium sulfide were used as the raw materials to synthesize the CdS nanoparticles through the thermochemical method. The obtained nanocomposite was characterized using FTIR, UV-vis., X-ray diffraction, and SEM techniques to get information about the formation of nanoparticles within the polymer matrix. The obtained results confirm the formation of nanoparticles and give information about their mean size. UV-Vis spectroscopy revealed that the obtained nanostructures are appropriate base materials for making optical and semiconductor devices. The novelty of this work is the introduction of the new approach for the recycling and utilization of the Nylon 6,6 based plastic wastes and their first-time use as a matrix for CdS nanoparticle synthesis through the thermochemical method.

Keywords: Nylon, cadmium sulfide, recycling, utilization, polymer nanocomposites.

Introduction

The semiconductor nanoparticles have received considerable attention from the scientific community due to their interesting size effects and a wide range of potential applications. CdS is a semiconductor with a band gap of 2.42 eV and it finds applications in the production of phosphors, solar cells, sensors, light-emitting diodes, photocatalyst materials, and lasers. They can be synthesized by different methods like the sol-gel process, gamma-irradiation method, electrochemical method, hydrothermal or solvothermal method, microemulsion, microwave, thermal evaporation, and the ultrasonic method [1-3].

The large surface-to-volume ratio of nanomaterials often results in aggregation, which can prevent their application. Various polymers, glasses, ceramics, and organic capping agents are used to overcome this problem by improving the stability of nanocrystals and reducing the surface defects [2,3].

Nylon 6,6 is polyamide that is used in the production of strong and stiff synthetic fibers, packaging substances, cable ties, as well as films, etc. This polymer material is thermoplastic which makes it available for recycling, but the high amount of production and application cause danger to the environment. The incineration process decreases the amount of natural raw material and needs high energy. The minimization of the Nylon wastes can reduce their environmental impacts. The solution to the problem can be found through the utilization of the Nylon wastes.

In this paper, we introduce using the Nylon 6,6 based plastic wastes as the matrices for the synthesis of the CdS nanoparticles and obtaining new polymer nanocomposites with useful properties. The origin of the used polymer is Nylon 6,6 cable tie waste. The Nylon 6,6 based polymer powders obtained from the cable tie wastes were used as the matrix in order to syn-

thesize CdS nanoparticles. Then the obtained Nylon/CdS polymer nanocomposite was investigated by different investigation techniques.

The novelty of this work is the introduction of the new approach for the recycling and utilization of the Nylon 6,6 based plastic wastes and their first-time use as a matrix for CdS nanoparticle synthesis through the thermochemical method. We aim (a) to explore the applicability of this new polymer matrix for CdS nanoparticle synthesis through the thermochemical method and (b) to investigate the influence of the CdS nanocrystals on the properties of the polymer matrix. The anticipated benefit of the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite is its applicability in solar cell and semiconductor fabrication.

Materials and methods

Preparation of matrix from nylon 6,6 based waste

The polymer matrix was prepared using Nylon 6,6 based pigment-free cable tie wastes. The cable ties were first washed, dried, mechanically ground with kitchen grinder and passed through a sieve to obtain the uniform polymer powders. Then, the polymer powder was sonicated under 35 kHz condition for 15 minutes to reduce its grain size, and also to get the pores and active parts inside the polymer grains. The obtained finer polymer powder was washed several times, filtered through a membrane filter (pore size=0.45 μ m), and dried under atmospheric conditions.

Thermochemical synthesis of the CdS nanoparticles within the nylon 6,6 matrix

0.1 M aqueous solution of CdCl₂ • 2.5H₂O was prepared using double-distilled water in a 50 ml volumetric flask. Then this solution was transferred to a 250 ml three-neck round-bottom flask and 2 grams of previously prepared Nylon 6,6 fine powder was added to it. The flask was connected to a reflux condenser and placed in a water bath. The temperature was gradually

raised to 90°C and the process was continued with stirring for 4 hours. After the completion, the mixture was gradually cooled in air, filtered through a membrane filter (pore size=0.45µm) in a Büchner funnel, washed several times with double-distilled water to remove the unreacted chemicals, transferred to a Petri dish, and dried under atmospheric conditions.

Then 0.1 M aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S} \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared using double-distilled water in a 50 ml volumetric flask and transferred to a 250 ml three-neck round-bottom flask. The previously prepared Nylon 6,6/ Cd_2^+ intermediate structure was added to the as-prepared solution of the sulfuration agent in the flask.

The flask was connected to a reflux condenser and placed in a water bath again. The temperature was gradually raised to 90°C and the process was continued with stirring for 2 hours. After the completion, the mixture was gradually cooled in air, filtered through a membrane filter (pore size=0.45µm) in a Büchner funnel, washed several times with double-distilled water to remove the unreacted chemicals, transferred to a Petri dish, and dried under atmospheric conditions.

The obtained polymer nanocomposite (Nylon 6,6/ CdS) was prepared for an investigation by various instrumental techniques.

Figure 1. The image of the Nylon 6,6 based waste cable tie (a), the powder obtained from that (b,c), and the Nylon 6,6/ CdS nanocomposite.

As shown in Figure 1, the white color turns yellow through the process which is the proof of the formation of CdS nanoparticles within the Nylon 6,6 polymer matrix.

Characterization

All the chemicals used in the synthesis of the CdS nanoparticles were of analytical reagent grades. The raw materials were purified before use by recrystallization. Double-distilled water was used as the solvent in all stages of the process. All experiments were conducted under an air atmosphere. The SEM, FTIR, XRD, and UV-vis. spectroscopy techniques were used to characterize the obtained nanostructures. VARIAN 3600 spectrophotometer was used to get the FTIR spectra of the samples ground in the KBr pellet. UV-vis. results for fine powder samples were taken using an integrating sphere by SPECORD 250 PLUS device. Powder XRD studies were carried out on a Rigaku MiniFlex Desktop X-ray diffractometer using CuK_α radiation with a 1.5418 Å wavelength. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images were taken by means of a JEOL JSM-6510LV device at 10 kV accelerating voltage.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the comparative FTIR spectra of the Nylon 6,6 based polymer matrix (a) and Nylon 6,6/ CdS nanocomposite (b) samples. The macromolecular chain of the Nylon 6,6 polymer contains the functionalities that possess carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen atoms. These functionalities are highly active to infrared irradiation, causing the corresponding characteristic peaks in the spectrum. The peaks corresponding to the C-C vibrations are clearly observed at 677 cm^{-1} , 929 cm^{-1} , 1029 cm^{-1} , 1043 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the pristine-Nylon 6.6 polymer (figure 2a). The peaks

corresponding to the carbonyl (C = O) groups derived from adipic acid residues are at 1627 cm^{-1} , 1635 cm^{-1} , 1647 cm^{-1} , 1668 cm^{-1} , 1701 cm^{-1} , 1718 cm^{-1} , and 1735 cm^{-1} . Peaks at 584 cm^{-1} , 1130 cm^{-1} , 1172 cm^{-1} , 1192 cm^{-1} , and 1259 cm^{-1} correspond to the C-N amide group. N-H deformation corresponding to the amide group shows itself with numerous peaks at 1361 cm^{-1} , 1458-1544 cm^{-1} interval, 1668-1851 cm^{-1} interval (N-H bending), and 3500-3900 cm^{-1} interval (asymmetric and symmetrical N-H deformation). The weak peaks for symmetrical and asymmetrical CH_2 deformation and symmetrical C-H deformation vibrations are observed at 2839 cm^{-1} , 2910 cm^{-1} , and 3053 cm^{-1} . The peaks around the wave numbers 1411 cm^{-1} , 1431 cm^{-1} , and 1475 cm^{-1} also correspond to the methylene groups (CH_2). In the process of making a matrix from Nylon 6.6-based plastic waste material, the mechanical grinding and ultrasonic treatment cause destruction in the polymer chain, which manifests itself in numerous peaks corresponding to the OH deformation in the region of 3500-3900 cm^{-1} interval [4-8].

The same peaks can also be seen in the FTIR spectrum of the Nylon 6,6/ CdS nanocomposite (figure 2b). It can be seen from the spectrum that the thermochemical synthesis of the CdS nanoparticles within the Nylon 6.6 polymer matrix changes the intensities of the peaks of the functionalities of the polymer. It can be explained by the formation of nanoparticles on these functional groups and the consequent change in their vibrational capacity under the influence of infrared radiation. The peaks for Cd-S deformation are also observed in the spectrum for Nylon 6,6/ CdS nanocomposite at 534 cm^{-1} , 580 cm^{-1} , 582 cm^{-1} , 638 cm^{-1} , and 717 cm^{-1} [1-3].

Figure 2. FTIR spectra of the Nylon 6,6 based polymer matrix (a) and Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite (b) samples.

The optical properties and the band gap of the synthesized materials were characterized by UV-vis spectroscopy. Figure 3 shows the transmittance spectra (A) and dependence of $[F(R)hv]^{1/2}$ on hv (B) for Nylon 6,6 based polymer matrix (1) and Nylon 6,6/CdS (2) samples. The Kubelka-Munk approach is applied in order to characterize the optical properties using the result from optical reflectance. The Kubelka-Munk equation is expressed as follows [3]:

$$F(R) = (1-R)^2 / 2R = k/s$$

where R is the absolute reflectance, k is the molar absorption coefficient and s is the scattering coefficient. The band gap energies (E_g) of the samples can be calculated by plotting the dependence of $[F(R)hv]^{1/2}$ on hv

and extrapolating the linear parts of the curves to the abscissa energy axis.

UV-vis spectra were recorded in the 190-1100 nm range and the band gap obtained from the dependence of the $[F(R)hv]^{1/2}$ on hv for the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite was 4.2 eV. This result is higher than that of bulk CdS (2.42 eV) and shows the blue shifting due to the crystalline size [9]. This rather broad band gap suggests that the nanocomposite could find applications in photovoltaic devices.

The average diameters of the CdS nanocrystals in Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite were calculated as 5.9 nm using the Brus equation [10].

Figure 3. UV-vis transmittance spectra (A) and dependence of $[F(R)hv]^{1/2}$ on hv (B) for Nylon 6,6 based polymer matrix (1) and Nylon 6,6/CdS (2) samples.

Figure 4 shows the X-ray diffraction pattern of Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite obtained by the thermochemical method. The peaks observed at 2θ angles of

20.54° , 23.63° , 38.18° , and 40.72° can be assigned to reflections from the characteristic (011), (021), (113), and (013) crystallographic planes of CdS nanoparticles,

respectively. The results were studied based on the 04-006-0809 and 04-004-1000 standard diffraction files of CdS and the obtained nanoparticles were proved to have two mixed phases like hexagonal and cubic crystal structures [1-3].

Scherrer's formula was used to calculate the average size of CdS nanoparticles synthesized by the thermochemical method within the Nylon 6,6 polymer matrix [3,11,12]. Calculations were made for each peak and the average value was taken. It was found that the average diameter of the synthesized nanoparticles is 2.76 nm.

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction pattern of Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite obtained by the thermochemical method.

SEM micrographs of the initial Nylon 6,6-based matrix and the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite samples, as well as Elemental mapping images of C, O, Cd, and S elements in the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite sample are depicted in figure 5. It can be seen from the images that the pristine Nylon 6,6 polymer exhibits a relatively smooth surface morphology. By synthesizing CdS nanoparticles, this smooth surface morphology

changes to a correspondingly rough form. From the image of the nanocomposite, the average sizes of CdS nanoparticles were visually determined and found to be consistent with those obtained by other methods.

The elemental mapping images show that the synthesized nanoparticles are uniformly distributed within the polymer. This proves that the synthesis is effective, including that the matrix and synthesis conditions are optimal for the synthesis of CdS nanoparticles.

Figure 5. SEM images of the initial Nylon 6,6-based matrix (a) and the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite (b) samples (A); Elemental mapping images of C, O, Cd, and S elements in the Nylon 6,6/CdS nanocomposite sample (B).

Conclusion

CdS nanoparticles were synthesized via the thermochemical technique. Nylon 6,6 based plastic waste materials were used as the matrix in order to get new polymer nanocomposite with unique properties and to find new utilization for the waste plastics. The success of formation of the polymer nanocomposite was confirmed by different characterization techniques like

FTIR, UV-vis., XRD, and SEM. The FTIR results show the anticipated bands related to the functionalities of the Nylon 6,6. The formation of the CdS nanoparticles within the matrix changes the intensities of the peaks and adds new peaks related to Cd-S deformation to the spectrum. The UV-vis results show 4.2 eV band gap which is higher than that of bulk CdS (2.42 eV). This

shifting to the higher energy state is evidence of the formation of CdS nanoparticles with 5.9 nm average diameter. The rather broad band gap suggests that the nanocomposite could find applications in photovoltaic devices. The XRD results revealed that the obtained nanoparticles are in 2.76 nm mean size and mixed hexagonal and cubic structure. The average sizes of CdS nanoparticles were visually determined also from SEM micrographs and found to be consistent with those obtained by other methods. The elemental mapping images show that the synthesized nanoparticles are uniformly distributed within the polymer which proves that the synthesis is effective, including that the matrix and synthesis conditions are optimal for the synthesis of CdS nanoparticles. All the obtained results show that the nylon 6,6 based plastic waste materials are suitable for application as the matrices for the CdS nanoparticle synthesis.

References

1. Malikov EY, Altay MC, Muradov MB, et al. Synthesis and characterization of CdS nanoparticle based multiwallcarbon nanotube–maleic anhydride–1-octene nanocomposites. *Physica E* 2015;69:212-218.
2. Akperov OH, Muradov MB, Malikov EY, et. Al. Synthesis and characterization of CdS nanocrystals in Maleic anhydride-Octene-1-Vinylbutyl Ether terpolymer matrix, *Physica E* 2016;81:150-155.
3. Malikov EY, Altay MC, Akperov OH, et al. Effect of sonication time on the synthesis of the CdS nanoparticle based multiwall carbon nanotube–maleic anhydride–1-octene nanocomposites. *Fuller. Nanotub. Car. N.* 2018;26(5):255-262.
4. Shiv Govind Prasad, Abhijit De, Udayan De, Structural and optical investigations of radiation damage in transparent PET polymer films // *International Journal of Spectroscopy*, 2011;2011:1-7.
5. Malikov EY. Potential semiconductor material based on the multiwall carbon nanotube–maleic anhydride–1-octene/SnS nanocomposite. *Compos. Interface.* 2021;27(5):465-478.
6. Malikov EY, Akperov OH, Muradov MB, et al. Facile synthesis route of graphene-like structures from multiwall carbon nanotubes. *Fuller. Nanotub. Car. N.* 2017; 25(9):540-544.
7. Malikov EY. Potential strengthening additive for cement mortar based on the maleic anhydride– α -octene functionalised multiwall carbon nanotube. *Int. J. Pavement. Eng.* 2021:1-6.
8. Malikov E.Y. The effect of polyvinyl alcohol functionalized multiwall carbon nanotubes on the improvement of the compressive strength of concrete. *Fuller Nanotub Car N* 2020;28(10):781-785.
9. Manickathai K, Viswanathan SK, Alagar M. Synthesis and characterization of CdO and CdS nanoparticles. *Indian J Pure Ap Phy* 2008;46:561-564.
10. Brus L. Electronic wave functions in semiconductor clusters: experiment and theory. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry* 1986;90(12):2555-2560.
11. Altay MC, Malikov EY, Eyvazova GM, et al. Facile synthesis of CuS nanoparticles deposited on polymer nanocomposite foam and their effects on microstructural and optical properties. *Eur. Polym. J.* 2015;68:47-56.
12. Malikov EY, Muradov MB, Akperov OH, et al. Synthesis and characterization of polyvinyl alcohol based multiwalled carbon nanotube nanocomposites. *Physica E* 2014;61:129-134.